

Supporting Information for:

Thermal Stability of Chalcogenide Perovskites

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1. Crystal phases, ionic radii and tolerance factors of studied halide and chalcogenide perovskites.

Table TS1. Crystal phase, ionic radii and tolerance factors of studied halide and chalcogenide perovskites.¹⁻³

Compound	Crystal phase	Lattice	Space group	Temp. range in K (°C)	r_A (Å)	r_B (Å)	r_X (Å)	r_{B^-} r_{X^-} (Å)	r_{B^-} r_{X^-} - r_B (deg.)	r_{B^-} r_{X^-} r_B (Å)	μ_o	t_F
MAPbI ₃	α-phase	Cubic	Pm3m	>330 (57)	2.17	1.03	2.2	3.15	180	6.3	0.468	0.957
	β-phase	Tetragonal	I4/mcm	160 to 330 (-113 to 57)	2.17	1.03	2.2	3.16-3.17	157-180	6.28-6.36	0.468	0.957
	γ-phase	Orthorhombic	Pnma	<160 (-113)	2.17	1.03	2.2	3.18-3.19	151-163	6.17-6.32	0.468	0.957
CsPbI ₃	δ-phase (needle-like)	Orthorhombic	Pnma	>298 (25)	1.78	1.03	2.2	3.09-3.43	88-94		0.468	0.871
	α-phase	Cubic	Pm3m	>578 (305)	1.88	1.03	2.2	3.15	180	6.29	0.468	0.893
	β-phase	Tetragonal	P4/mbm	<578 (305)	1.88	1.03	2.2	3.15-3.16	162-180	6.24-6.29	0.468	0.893
	γ-phase	Orthorhombic	Pnma	~448 (175)	1.88	1.03	2.2	3.17-3.18	152-160	6.17-6.29	0.468	0.893
BaZrS ₃	Distorted PS	Orthorhombic	Pnma	>893.15 (520)	1.61	0.72	1.84	2.57-2.62	157-160	4.98-4.99	0.391	0.952
		Tetragonal	I4 ₁ /acd	<933.15 (560)	1.61	0.72	1.84	-	-	-	0.391	0.952
SrZrS ₃	Needle-like	Orthorhombic	Pnma	<1253 (980)	1.31	0.72	1.84	2.54-2.57	95	-	0.391	0.870
	Distorted PS	Orthorhombic	Pnma	>1293 (1020)	1.44	0.72	1.84	2.52-2.53	147-150	4.88-4.89	0.391	0.905
BaHfS ₃	Distorted PS	Orthorhombic	Pnma		1.61	0.71	1.84	2.55-2.6	147-148	4.97-4.98	0.385	0.956
SrHfS ₃	Distorted PS	Orthorhombic	Pnma		1.44	0.71	1.84	2.51-2.53	148-150	4.87-4.88	0.385	0.909

2. Lattice parameters comparison of studied halide and chalcogenide perovskites

Table TS2. Lattice parameter comparison of studied halide and chalcogenide perovskites.⁴⁻⁶

Composition	Crystal phase	$a(\text{\AA})$	$b(\text{\AA})$	$c(\text{\AA})$	α (°)	β (°)	γ (°)	$V(\text{\AA}^3)$	tilting ^a (axis)	octahedra rotation ^b
MAPbI ₃	α -phase	6.3063(2)	6.3063(2)	6.3063(2)	90	90	90	250.80(1)	0	0
	β -phase	8.8117(8)	8.8117(8)	12.674(2)	90	90	90	984.1(2)	0	11.332
	γ -phase	8.8767(9)	12.640(1)	8.588(1)	90	90	90	963.6(2)	5.462	16.005
δ -CsPbI ₃	δ -phase	10.4500(5)	4.7965(2)	17.760(8)	90	90	90	890.20(7)	N/A	N/A
	α -phase	6.2965	6.2965	6.2965	90	90	90	249.64(0)	0	0
	β -phase	8.8269	8.8269	6.299	90	90	90	490.78(0)	0	8.643
	γ -phase	8.8518	8.6198	12.501	90	90	90	953.85(1)	9.870	10.750
BaZrS ₃	DP	7.064(2)	9.975(4)	7.029(2)	90	90	90	495.04	9.366	8.301
BaZrS ₃ ^c	tetragonal (I4 ₁ /acd)	7.0741(8)	7.0741(8)	10.104(2)	90	90	90	505.63	–	–
SrZrS ₃	NL	8.5254(7)	3.8255(3)	13.924(12)	90	90	90	454.14(6)	N/A	N/A
SrZrS ₃	DP	7.1085(4)	9.7661(5)	6.7350(3)	90	90	90	467.56(4)	15.099	11.137
BaHfS ₃	DP	7.002(6)	9.915(6)	6.995(6)	90	90	90	485.63(66)	14.898	12.885
BaHfS ₃ ^d	tetragonal (I4 ₁ /acd)	7.0383(9)	7.0383(9)	10.0578(6)	90	90	90	498.26	–	–
SrHfS ₃	DP	7.051(4)	9.716(4)	6.718(3)	90	90	90	460.23(38)	15.153	14.095

^aAngle between plane through equatorial sulfur atoms in the same octahedra and plane [010]

^bAngle between two opposite equatorial sulfur atoms within two octahedra and plane [100]

^cLattice parameters calculated from XRD pattern measured at 590 °C

^dLattice parameters calculated from XRD pattern measured at 560 °C

3. XRD of needle-like phases

Fig. S1. XRD of as-synthesized pure needle-like phase α -EuZrS₃ and α -SrZrS₃.

4. TG/DTA of needle-like phases

Figure S2. Mass change and DTA of prepared needlelike phases

5. TG/DTA of distorted perovskites by using 1 °C/min

Figure S3. Mass change of prepared CP phases with the heating rate 1 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$.

6. Temperature-dependent XRD under inert atmosphere

Figure S4. HT XRD patterns of BaZrS_3 (a), $\beta\text{-SrZrS}_3$ (b), recorded in the temperature range 400–700 °C and 500–700 °C, respectively. The measurements were performed under vacuum ($\sim 5 \times 10^{-4}$ mbar) and nitrogen atmosphere, respectively. The heating rate between the data collections was 8 °C/min. The data collection time at each data point was 10 min. for BaZrS_3 and 1 min. for $\beta\text{-SrZrS}_3$. The temperature was held constant during the data acquisition.

7. Temperature-dependent XRD patterns of BaZrS₃ and BaHfS₃

Figure S5. Temperature dependent XRD for BaZrS₃ in the temperature range 490–590 °C and BaHfS₃ in the temperature range 400–450 °C.

8. XRD of needle-like phases after thermal analysis

Figure S6. XRD of α -SrZrS₃, α -EuZrS₃ (needle-like phases) after thermal analysis

9. EDS of distorted perovskites

Figure S7. EDS traces of BaZrS₃ (a) and β-SrZrS₃ before and after oxidation. Samples were washed with methanol before and after oxidation.

10. Short-term thermal stability of the needle-like phases

Figure S8. Comparison of the short-term thermal stability of α -SrZrS₃ and α -EuZrS₃ at 100 °C (a) 300 °C (b), and 500 °C (c) in air. The data points represent a total area of multiple XRD peaks associated with a particular phase, relative to the total area of the same peaks in the as prepared sample.

11. Distributions of the sizes of the CP grains used in the short-term thermal stability experiment

Figure S9. Distributions of the sizes of the CP grains used in the short-term thermal stability experiment. The grain size distribution of the CP powder samples was estimated using a series of SEM images. The size of the individual grains was estimated as the diameter of the area assigned by ImageJ software using the image contrast threshold. For the measurement, the powders were dispersed on clean surface silicon substrates cleaned by sonication in acetone, isopropyl alcohol, and deionized water (each for 5 min maintained at 50 ° C) and air dried.

12. Tauc plot of all the prepared ternary chalcogenides

Figure S10. Tauc plot of the reflectance spectra of all the prepared ternary chalcogenides. F(R) is Kubelka-Munk function.

13. Diffuse reflectance of needle-like phases

Figure S11. Diffuse reflectance of as prepared α -SrZrS₃, α -EuZrS₃ with 800 °C short exposure and 168 h long term heat exposure.

14. Safety consideration of lead (Pb) containing compounds

Lead iodide or lead oxide are carcinogenic/fetal if swallowed or inhaled. Lead iodide sublimes at ~400 °C in inert atmosphere therefore the gas outlet of the thermal analyzer should end in the vented area (fumehood, vented cabinet). In air the lead iodide oxidizes at around ~600 °C to form lead oxides, these are left in crucible in powder form. After experiment and analysis, it should be disposed appropriately to avoid the environment pollution.

15. References

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